

THE DEVELOPMENT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE TEACHING PROFESSION

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Abstract. *This article explores the significance of emotional intelligence in the teaching profession and its role in fostering effective teacher-student relationships. Drawing from a variety of sources, this study delves into the concept of emotional intelligence, highlighting its relevance and application in pedagogical contexts. It investigates how teachers with well-developed emotional intelligence excel in perceiving and addressing students' emotional needs, thus improving overall educational outcomes. The research discusses how emotional intelligence positively influences professional and personal success, emphasizing its growing importance in the education and professional development of teaching professionals.*

Keywords: *emotional intelligence, teaching profession, teacher-student relationships, pedagogy, emotional understanding, emotion management, educational outcomes, professional development.*

Аннотация. *В этой статье исследуется значение эмоционального интеллекта в профессии педагога и его роль в укреплении эффективных отношений между учителем и учениками. В нем исследуется, как учителя с хорошо развитым эмоциональным интеллектом преуспевают в восприятии эмоциональных потребностей учащихся и удовлетворении их потребностей, тем самым улучшая общие результаты обучения. В исследовании обсуждается, как эмоциональный интеллект положительно влияет на профессиональный и личный успех, подчеркивается его растущее значение в образовании и профессиональном развитии педагогов-профессионалов.*

Ключевые слова: *эмоциональный интеллект, профессия учителя, взаимоотношения учителя и ученика, педагогика, управление эмоциями, результаты образования, профессиональное развитие.*

Success in a person's professional life is closely linked to their knowledge, skills, erudition, and general thinking. However, in most cases, high general intelligence is not sufficient. The effectiveness of a young professional engaged in "subject-subject" relationships partly depends on their ability to recognize and manage their own emotions as well as understand the emotions of others.

For educators, emotional intelligence represents one of the key criteria determining success in their professional endeavors. This is particularly relevant due to the nuances of interaction with students, where the teacher's ability to clearly recognize and understand not only their own emotions but also the emotional states of their students become crucial. Furthermore, teachers must exhibit empathy, sympathy, and the ability to anticipate emotional reactions, including responses to various emotional stimuli [7].

Within the framework of socio-emotional education, educators who actively develop their emotional intelligence skills are better equipped to exhibit desired behavior, apply principles based on emotional intelligence in everyday situations, and facilitate interpersonal problem-solving and conflict resolution [2].

Teachers possessing the ability for pedagogical thinking, characterized as divergent in nature and content, can actively transform pedagogical information and transcend the established time parameters in the pedagogical reality. The effectiveness of a teacher's professional activity depends to a considerable extent not only on their knowledge and skills but rather on their ability to apply available information in pedagogical situations in various ways and at an accelerated pace. Developed emotional intelligence enables teachers to not merely perceive isolated facts and phenomena in the pedagogical sphere but, rather, to comprehend pedagogical concepts, theories of teaching and educating students in their entirety and complexity.

Research conducted by Daniel Goleman [3] reveals that a high level of emotional intelligence significantly contributes to both an individual's professional and personal success. The phenomenon of emotional intelligence, its structure, and conditions for development have been studied by both foreign (such as J. Matthews, R.D. Roberts, S.J. Stein, and others) and domestic (including I.N. Andreeva, D.V. Lyusin, M.A. Manoylova, M.A. Spasskaya, and more) scholars.

Emotional intelligence can be defined as a psychological trait that serves as the foundation for emotional self-regulation. It encompasses a set of emotionally intelligent abilities, including understanding and managing one's own emotions and those of others, as well as responding effectively to the demands of the surrounding environment.

In her research, I.N. Andreeva notes that emotional intelligence is the subject of intensive study in the field of psychology, both in foreign and domestic scientific circles. It constitutes a complex of mental abilities that enable individuals to recognize and understand themselves. It is emotional intelligence that allows internal movement towards the awareness and comprehension of the reasons for various emotions, as well as exerting a significant influence on oneself and others, in other words, managing one's own and others' emotions [1].

According to the two-component theory by D.V. Lyusin [4], emotional intelligence encompasses two key aspects: the ability to understand emotions, both one's own and those of others, and the ability to manage them, both one's own and others' emotions.

Given the focus of our article, we attach significant importance to the concept of J. Mayer, P. Caruso, and P. Salovey, who consider emotional intelligence on two levels: as a cognitive ability and as a combined model of cognitive abilities and personality traits. They define emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive and evoke emotions, enhance thinking effectiveness through emotions, understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and reflexively manage emotions to ensure emotional and intellectual development [6].

Contemporary psychological literature actively explores aspects related to the examination of individual personality traits and abilities that are relevant in the context of emotional intelligence. For instance, F.N. Gonoblin highlighted a series of professionally significant abilities in teachers, such as the ability to understand students, possess pedagogical tact, engage in creative work, react quickly to pedagogical situations, and conduct themselves effectively in them, among other characteristics. D. Rains pointed out that successful teachers can be distinguished from less successful ones based on several features, including a positive attitude towards students, a focus on children in the process of education, a high level of verbal understanding, emotional stability, an interest in interactions and friendliness, as well as responsibility and diligence. G. Miller provides data indicating that teachers with a high level of professional mastery exhibit greater self-confidence, lower susceptibility to neuroticism and anxiety [5].

Emotional intelligence consists of four key components:

Perceiving and Expressing Emotions: This involves the ability to perceive, recognize, and express emotions, both one's own and those of others. It includes the capacity to recognize emotions through physical states, feelings, and thoughts, as well as accurately and adequately expressing one's emotions and related needs. It also encompasses the ability to differentiate between sincere and false displays of feelings.

Managing Thoughts: This pertains to the ability to evoke specific emotions and control them, influencing how emotions interact with the cognitive system and affect thoughts. Emotions direct attention to important aspects of information, enhance analytical capabilities, and affect memory concerning feelings. Different emotional states can influence problem-solving abilities differently.

Understanding Emotions: This component involves the ability to comprehend complex emotions and transitions between them. It also includes the capacity to analyze emotions and apply emotional knowledge. Understanding emotions encompasses classifying emotions, recognizing connections between words and emotions, interpreting the significance of emotions in the context of relationships, and comprehending complex emotional states, including ambivalent experiences.

Regulating One's Own and Others' Emotions: This aspect of emotional intelligence encompasses the capacity to reflexively manage emotions, which is essential to maintain openness to both positive and negative feelings. It also involves the ability to evoke or restrain emotions as necessary, depending on the usefulness or informativeness of the emotions. Emotional intelligence includes being aware of emotions, determining their clarity, typicality, appropriateness, and more, as well as managing one's own emotions and the emotions of others by restraining negative feelings and activating positive ones without distorting the content of the emotions.

In this way, emotional intelligence, consisting of these four key components—perceiving and expressing emotions, managing thoughts, understanding emotions, and regulating one's own and others' emotions—plays a crucial role in the pedagogical context. The perception and understanding of emotions enable teachers to better interact with students, while the management and regulation of emotions contribute to successful pedagogical activities, particularly in resolving interpersonal conflicts and creating a supportive educational environment. Emotional intelligence significantly influences the professional behavior of educators and their ability to effectively engage with students in various situations.

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